

EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MATHEMATICAL ANXIETY AND SELF-EFFICACY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12609074>

ABSTRACT

This descriptive-correlational research aimed to investigate the relationship between mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy among 62 Grade 10 students at Mulapula National High School. Simple random sampling was used to determine the participants of the study. Data collection involved the use of the ERUNT for self-efficacy assessment and a 25-item survey questionnaire for mathematical anxiety. This 25-item researchers-made questionnaire underwent validation and item analysis. Independent variables included sex and sections, while dependent variables comprised mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy levels. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, and standard deviation were utilized, along with inferential statistics like the T-test and Pearson's r , with a significance level set at 0.05. Results revealed variations in mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy concerning sex and sections. Male exhibited higher mathematical anxiety levels than females, and section A students reported lower anxiety levels than section B counterparts. Conversely, self-efficacy levels were higher among females compared to males, with section A students surpassing those in section B. The study concluded a significant relationship between mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy. Based on the discoveries presented, the subsequent suggestions and recommendations are proposed with the intention of creating a supportive setting for students to overcome mathematical anxiety and boost their self-efficacy.

Keywords: *Mathematical Anxiety, Self-efficacy*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is often challenging for many students, leading to mathematics anxiety. Yet, there is limited research on its relationship with self-efficacy. As stated in PISA (2018), the Philippines ranked low in math and science education quality, with students struggling to comprehend questions. This is evidenced by below-target National Achievement Test (NAT) scores and low average scores in Mathematical Literacy compared to OECD countries. High levels of math anxiety were noted even among top-performing students, impacting their performance from an early age.

Math anxiety involves feelings of fear, tension, and apprehension specific to math tasks. It is consistent across various mathematical contexts and prevalent in both K-12 and tertiary education. This anxiety can diminish academic performance and self-efficacy, which is a person's belief in their ability to complete tasks and achieve goals. Factors like these suggest a need for focused research and interventions to help students manage anxiety and build confidence in their mathematical abilities (Luttenberger et al, 2019).

The study aimed to provide insights and recommendations to create a supportive environment for Grade 10 students at Mulapula National High School to overcome math anxiety and enhance self-efficacy. By examining the relationship between these factors, the researchers hope to contribute to improved academic performance and positive attitudes toward mathematics among students, thus aiding in the advancement of math education in the Philippines.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the level between mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy of the students.

Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents when taken as a whole and when classified as to sex and sections?
2. What is the level of mathematical anxiety of the respondents as an entire group and when classified as to sex and sections?
3. What is the level of self-efficacy of the respondents as an entire group and when classified as to sex and sections?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of the mathematical anxiety of the respondents when classified as to sex and sections?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of self-efficacy of the respondents when classified as to sex and sections?
6. Is there a significant relationship between mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy of the respondents?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative research method with an emphasis on the descriptive-correlational design. A descriptive correlational design is a research method that examines the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them (Baht, 2023).

Descriptive-correlational research design was used to determine the level of mathematics anxiety and self-efficacy of Grade 10 students of Mulapula National High School for the academic year 2023-2024. The researcher chose sixty-two Grade 10 students from Mulapula National High School for the school year 2023-2024 as the respondents.

In this study, the researchers were able to randomly choose the respondents from the population of Grade 10 students through simple random sampling. The researchers aimed to assess the Mathematical Anxiety and Self-Efficacy of Grade 10 students, using a questionnaire adapted from the Department of Education's Electronic Regional Unified Numeracy Test (E-RUNT) results. The data-gathering instrument utilized for the study consisted of a researcher-made and expertly validated survey questionnaire checklist for Mathematical Anxiety and an adapted E-RUNT results for Self-Efficacy to collect necessary data for Grade 10 students during the academic year 2023-2024. The researchers developed a 25-item survey questionnaire checklist for the Mathematical Anxiety of Grade 10 students, divided into two parts. The instrument underwent expert consultation and validation before being implemented for face-to-face testing with a randomly selected group of students.

Upon obtaining permission from the Dean of the School of Teacher Education to conduct research outside the school, the researchers sent a letter to the College President. After the letters were signed, the researchers sent a letter to the DepEd School Division Office of Passi City for pilot testing of the research instrument. The data was then sent to the statistician for a reliability test. After the statistician confirmed that the research instrument was reliable for the study, the researcher sent a letter to the principal of Mulapula National High School for the conduct of the study. A face-to-face implementation was observed for one day. The selected respondents of the study were chosen through simple random sampling, and the researchers distributed the questionnaire. The students were given 30 minutes to answer the questions included in the instrument. After conducting the study, the information will be gathered and checked by the assigned statistician for interpretation and analysis of the data.

RESULTS

Profile of the Respondents in Mulapula National High School. The table presents an overview of the respondent profile, comprising 62 respondents. Notably, there is a greater representation of females, accounting for 37 respondents (59.7%), compared to males, who constitute 25 respondents (40.3%). In terms of section distribution, an equal

participation rate is observed, with both Section A and Section B each having 31 respondents, representing 50% of the total respondents. These results confirm the study by Becker (2018) that women are more likely to respond to surveys and are also more likely to use support forums. Particularly for mail or web surveys, it is frequently found that women are more likely to respond than men.

Table 1.

Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Sex	Male	25	40.3
	Female	37	59.7
	Total	62	100.0

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Section	A	31.0	50.0
	B	31.0	50.0
	Total	62.0	100.0

Level of Mathematical Anxiety by Gender and Section. The results show the level of mathematical anxiety among grade ten learners at Mulapula National High School as a whole ($M=3.38$, $SD=0.54$), which is interpreted as "High Mathematics Anxiety." When grouped by gender, males have a higher level ($M=3.52$, $SD=0.66$), also interpreted as "High Mathematics Anxiety," compared to females ($M=3.28$, $SD=0.43$). Furthermore, when respondents are grouped by section, Section B ($M=3.40$, $SD=0.66$) has a higher level than Section A ($M=3.35$, $SD=0.40$). These findings support a study by Homayouni et al. (2022) which showed that there are differences between males and females in math anxiety and learning mathematics. Males scored higher in math anxiety assessment and also scored higher in learning mathematics compared to females.

Table 2.

Level of Mathematical Anxiety as to Sex and Sections

Group	Categories	N	Mean	Std.	Description
As a whole		62	3.38	0.54	High Mathematics Anxiety
Sex	Male	25	3.52	0.66	High Mathematics Anxiety
	Female	37	3.28	0.43	High Mathematics Anxiety

Section					
	Section A	31	3.35	0.66	High Mathematics Anxiety
	Section B	31	3.40	0.40	High Mathematics Anxiety

Legend: 4.1-5.0- Severe Mathematics Anxiety; 3.1-4.0 High Mathematics Anxiety; 2.1-3.0-Moderate Mathematics Anxiety; 1.1-2.0-Low Mathematics Anxiety; 0-1.0-Non-Mathematics Anxiety

Level of Self-Efficacy of Learners. The results show the level of self-efficacy among grade ten learners at Mulapula National High School when taken as a whole (M=32.06, SD=5.65), which is interpreted as "High Self-efficacy." When grouped according to sex, males have a mean score of (M=31.04, SD=5.29), also interpreted as "High Self-efficacy," which is slightly lower than females (M=32.76, SD=5.29), also interpreted as "High Self-efficacy." Additionally, when respondents were grouped according to section, Section A (M=32.90, SD=4.79) had a higher mean score than Section B (M=31.23, SD=6.36). The results of the study support the study conducted by Ildil, Apriani, Yendi, and Rangka (2016) indicating that male students have moderate self-efficacy while female students have high self-efficacy. Furthermore, the study highlights a significant difference in self-efficacy between male and female students, particularly among male students as their self-efficacy appears to be lower than that of female students.

Table 3
Level of Self-efficacy as to Sex and Sections

Group	Categories	N	Mean	Std.	Description
Sex	Male	25	31.04	6.11	High Self-efficacy
	Female	37	32.76	5.29	High Self-efficacy
	Total	62	32.06	5.65	High Self-efficacy
Section	Section A	31	32.90	4.79	High Self-efficacy
	Section B	31	31.23	6.36	High Self-efficacy
	Total	62	32.06	5.65	High Self-efficacy

Legend: 31.0-40.0-High Self-efficacy; 21.0-30.0- Moderate High Self-efficacy; 11.0-20.0- Moderate Self-efficacy; 1.0-10.0-Low Self-efficacy; 0-1.0-Very Low Self-efficacy

Difference in the Level of Mathematical Anxiety Among Learners as to Sex and Section. There is a study conducted to determine the difference in the level of mathematical anxiety among learners when classified according to their sex and section. Table 4 presents the T-test results, which reveal that there is no significant difference in the level of mathematical anxiety as to sex ($p=0.22$, $p<0.05$). Similarly, when considering the section, there is no significant difference in the level of mathematical anxiety ($p=0.74$, $p<0.05$). These findings support a study conducted by Lacia, Ben, and Elizar (2020), which investigated the mathematics anxiety score between males and females in the central part of the Philippines. The study found a significant difference between the anxiety levels of males and females, despite the very small difference in their magnitude. The mean score shows that male students are slightly higher than female students.

Table 4.
Difference Level of Mathematical Anxiety as to Sex and Section

Group	Mean	Mean Diff	df	T-value	Sig-value	Decision
Sex						
Male	3.52					
Female	3.28					
		0.24	97.7	3.27	0.22	Not Significant
Section						
A	3.36					
B	3.40					
		-.05	97.7	-.34	0.74	Not Significant

*Significant @ $p<0.05$

Difference in the Level of Self-Efficacy of Learners as to Sex and Section. There is a difference in the level of self-efficacy among the respondents when classified by sex and section. Table 5 shows that the T-test results revealed no significant difference in the level of self-efficacy as to sex ($p = 0.5$, $p < 0.05$). Similarly, there is no significant difference in the level of self-efficacy as to section ($p = 0.25$, $p < 0.05$). This study supports a study conducted by Bangga (2021), which revealed that both male and female students have a high level of self-efficacy. From the study of Baji (2020), it was found that there was no significant difference in academic self-efficacy between male and female students. However, the mean value of females indicates a higher level of self-efficacy than male students.

Table 5.
Difference Level of Self-efficacy as to Sex and Section

Group	Mean	Mean Diff.	Df	T-value	Sig-value	Decision
Sex						
Male	31.04					
Female	32.76					
		-1.72	106.56	-2.32	0.5	Not Significant
Section						
A	32.90					
B	331.23					
		1.68	115.74	1.17	0.25	Not Significant

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

Relationship Between the Level of Mathematical Anxiety and Self-Efficacy. The table shows the relationship between the level of mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy of Grade 10 learners at Mulapula National High School. The results show that there is a significant negative correlation ($r = -0.339$) between mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy for the entire group. These findings are supported by the study of Khasawneh, Gosling, and Williams (2021), which confirmed that the paramedic student cohort's self-efficacy levels and math anxiety had a significant negative correlation. Math anxiety and self-efficacy are significantly influenced by gender. To improve math performance and reduce anxiety during calculation tasks, such as dose determinations, targeted education should be developed to improve math self-efficacy.

Table 6
Relationship between the level of mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy

	Mathematical anxiety r value	P value	Description
Self-efficacy	-.339	0.01	Significant

DISCUSSION

The study involved a diverse group of participants from Grade ten at Mulapula National High School, with both genders and sections adequately represented. The majority of respondents were females, while males made up a significant proportion. Both sections contributed equally to the overall participant, ensuring a balanced representation across the various groups in the study.

The overall level of mathematical anxiety among Grade ten learners at Mulapula National

High School revealed a consensus categorized as "High Mathematics Anxiety". Males generally displayed a higher level of mathematical anxiety than females, and within sections, students in Section B tended to express slightly higher mathematical anxiety compared to those in Section A.

The overall level of self-efficacy among Grade ten learners at Mulapula National High School was broadly characterized as "High Self-efficacy". Specifically, when considering both sex and section, females tended to exhibit a higher level of proficiency compared to males. Additionally, when examining sections, students in Section A demonstrated a slightly higher mean score, falling within the "High Self-efficacy" category, compared to those in Section B.

The analysis of mathematical anxiety among Grade ten learners at Mulapula National High School, concerning sex differences, revealed that there is no significant difference in their mathematical anxiety levels. Similarly, when examining the impact of the school section on mathematical anxiety, the results indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in the mathematical anxiety levels of Grade ten learners at Mulapula National High School.

The examination of self-efficacy levels among Grade ten learners at Mulapula National High School, considering sex differences, indicated that there is no significant difference in their self-efficacy levels. Similarly, when exploring the impact of school section on self-efficacy, the findings suggest that there is no significant difference in the self-efficacy levels of Grade ten learners at Mulapula National High School.

The results on the relationship between the level of mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy showed that mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy are negatively correlated.

Conclusions

Based on the findings from the study, researchers consistently found that more females participated as respondents to the study, and an equal distribution was maintained across the two sections, ensuring a balanced representation of both genders and sections in the overall sample of 62 respondents. These results confirm the study by Becker (2018) that women are more likely to respond to surveys and are also more likely to use support forums. Particularly for mail or web surveys, it is frequently found that women are more likely to respond than men.

It has been found in the study that the level of mathematical anxiety of grade ten learners at Mulapula National High for the school year 2022-2023. Students express agreement in experiencing negative emotions when confronted with mathematical problems, categorizing their overall level of mathematical anxiety as "High Mathematics Anxiety."

Moreover, the analysis indicates that males, on average, exhibit a higher level of mathematical anxiety compared to females. Additionally, when comparing the sections, it

was observed that respondents in Section A reported a lower mean, suggesting a slightly lower level of mathematical anxiety than their counterparts in Section B. These findings support a study by Homayouni et al. (2022) which showed that there are differences between males and females in math anxiety and learning mathematics. Males scored higher in math anxiety assessment and also scored higher in learning mathematics compared to females.

Furthermore, when the researchers examined the data based on sex and sections, the level of self-efficacy of Grade 10 learners at Mulapula National High School as a whole was "High Self-efficacy". Notably, females demonstrated a higher mean perception than males, indicating a more elevated level of self-efficacy among female students.

Similarly, when examining the sections, it was observed that respondents in Section A reported a higher mean compared to Section B. Consequently, these findings suggest that both females and students in Section A interpret their self-efficacy as "High Self-efficacy."

The results of the study support the study conducted by Ildil, Apriani, Yendi, and Rangka (2016) indicating that male students have moderate self-efficacy while female students have high self-efficacy. Furthermore, the study highlights a significant difference in self-efficacy between male and female students, particularly among male students as their self-efficacy appears to be lower than that of female students.

The study reveals the difference in the level of mathematical anxiety as related to sex showed that there is no significant difference in the level of mathematical anxiety of grade ten learners at Mulapula National High School. It simply implies that males are more anxious than females. Similarly, the results also find that there is no significant difference in the section. Therefore, the study has found that the level of mathematical anxiety as a whole is "High Mathematics Anxiety". These findings support a study conducted by Lacia, Ben, and Elizar (2020), which investigated the mathematics anxiety score between males and females in the central part of the Philippines. The study found a significant difference between the anxiety levels of males and females, despite the very small difference in their magnitude. The mean score shows that male students are slightly higher than female students.

Moreover, the findings also reveal that there is no significant difference in the level of self-efficacy among the respondents according to sex and section. This simply implies that females have more numeracy foundational skills in learning all mathematical competencies than males. Therefore, as a whole and according to sex and section, the study states that it is interpreted as "High Self-efficacy". This study supports a study conducted by Bangga (2021), which revealed that both male and female students have a high level of self-efficacy. From the study of Baji (2020), it was found that there was no significant difference in academic self-efficacy between male and female students. However, the mean value of females indicates a higher level of self-efficacy than male students.

This study shows the results on the relationship between the level of mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy of Mulapula National High School. The results show that there is a negative correlation between Mathematical Anxiety and Self-efficacy. In essence, the results also show that there is a significant relationship between mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy.

Therefore, when considering the entire dataset and when classified by sex and sections, the interpretation remains consistent, categorizing the relationship between mathematical anxiety and self-efficacy as "High Mathematics Anxiety". These findings are supported by the study of Khasawneh, Gosling, and Williams (2021), which confirmed that the paramedic student cohort's self-efficacy levels and math anxiety had a significant negative correlation. Math anxiety and self-efficacy are significantly influenced by gender. To improve math performance and reduce anxiety during calculation tasks, such as dose determinations, targeted education should be developed to improve math self-efficacy.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. For students, this study results highlight the impact of mathematical anxiety on students. It is recommended that students collaborate to identify the root causes of mathematical fear. Introduce relaxation techniques, mindfulness exercises, or other stress-reduction methods to alleviate anxiety related to mathematics.
2. For parents, understand and realize the vital role they play in the education of their children. Parents must create a supportive environment where children feel comfortable seeking help when facing math challenges. Celebrate their progress and efforts to boost their confidence in tackling mathematical problems.
3. For DepEd, would plan better ways and implement targeted interventions at Mulapula National High School to overcome mathematical anxiety and enhance self-efficacy of the students. Suggest incorporating personalized learning approaches, peer collaboration, mentorship program, and real-world applications to make the sessions engaging.
4. For teachers, since the level of Mathematical Anxiety is higher and it has high self-efficacy, teachers promote more student engagement and active involvement in math-related activities can enhance their confidence in the subject. To address anxiety and stress, educators should arrange extracurricular activities and offer suitable counseling support for students. Encourage teachers to support peer-to-peer tutoring so that both the tutor and tutee can enhance their communication skills through the tutoring process, a valuable skill in academics and beyond.
5. For future researchers, the outcomes of this study on the Relationship between Mathematical Anxiety and Self-efficacy among Grade 10 students at Mulapula National

High School can serve as a valuable foundation for future researchers. It provides a starting point for those interested in delving deeper into the critical issues of mathematics anxiety and self-efficacy within the school context. Building upon these findings, future researchers can refine interventions, expand this scope, and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of how to address these significant concerns in education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, strict adherence to ethical standards was maintained throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's purpose and procedures. Respondents were explicitly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any negative repercussions. Anonymity was rigorously upheld, with all personal identifiers removed to protect the identities of the participants. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded at all times, ensuring that their participation did not cause any harm or distress. There were no conflicts of interest influencing the conduct of the study, and the researchers ensured that all findings were presented objectively without bias. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, with all sources and references appropriately cited. The results of the study were utilized solely for academic and research purposes, contributing to the understanding of the students. Through these measures, the researchers ensured the highest standards of ethical integrity in the study.

REFERENCES

- Bhat, A. (2023, November 24). Descriptive Correlational: Descriptive vs Correlational Research. QuestionPro. <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/descriptive-research-vs-correlational-research/>
- Baji, M. I. (2020). ANALYSIS OF GENDER DIFFERENCE IN ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY AND ACHIEVEMENTS AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN NIGER STATE, NIGERIA. *PEOPLE: International Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(3), 659–675. <https://doi.org/10.20319/pijss.2020.53.659675>
- Bangga, D. (2021). Senior high school students' self-efficacy and its relation to engagement in online class setting in a private university in the south of Metro Manila. *Science Education International*, 32(4), 302–307.
- Becker, R. (2021). Gender and Survey Participation An Event History Analysis of the Gender Effects of Survey Participation in a Probability-based Multi-wave Panel Study with a Sequential Mixed-mode Design. University of Bern, pp. 1-29. DOI: 10.12758/mda.2021.08
- Homayouni, A., Gharib, K., Mazini, F., Otaghsara, A.K. (2022). Comparative investigation of mathematics anxiety and learning mathematics in male and female students of distance education system. *International Journal of Teaching and Education*, Vol. II (No. 2).

- Ifdil.I., Apriani, R. Yendi, F.M., and Bolo Rangka, I.(2016). Level of Student's Self-efficacy Based on Gender. *Counsendu: The Internstional Journal of Counseling and Education*, 1(1), 29-33. DOI:10.23916/29-33.0016-11-i4lb
- Khasawneh, E., Gosling, C. and Williams, B. What impact does maths anxiety have on university students? *BMC Psychol* 9, 37 (2021). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-021-00537-2>
- Lacia, M. V., ben, f., and Elizar, E., (2020). Examining the Gender and Grade Level Differences in Mathematics Anxiety.
- Luttenberger, S., Wimmer, S., and Paechter, M. (2018). Spotlight on math anxiety. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, Volume 11, 311-322 <https://doi.org/10.2147/PRBM.S141421>
- OECD (2019), PISA 2018 Assessment and Analytical Framework, PISA, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/b25efab8-en>.